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Research Article

**COMPARING FEELINGS OF LONELINESS COGNITIVE
DISTORTIONS AND ATTITUDES TOWARD LIFE IN WOMEN
WITH SECOND WIFE AND ORDINARY WIFE OF SHIRAZ**Somayyeh Kargar Dolatabadi¹ and Nazanin Honarparvaran^{2*}¹Department of Counseling, Marvdasht Branch, Islamic Azad University, Marvdasht, Iran^{2*}Assistant professor, Department of Counseling, Marvdasht Branch, Islamic Azad University, Marvdasht, Iran*Corresponding Author Email: nazanin48@gmail.com**Abstract:**

The present study compared the feeling of loneliness, cognitive distortions and attitudes toward life in the second wife and ordinary wife of Shiraz. In terms of the nature and objectives, the research is of causal-comparative (post-event) type and the statistical population includes 70 second wife-women who are targeted by sampling method And 70 normal women by multistage cluster sampling that was selected after homogenization (age, education, social class). To collect data, questionnaires were used to assess the emotional self-sufficiency of adults, Abdullah Zadeh cognitive distortions; attitudes toward the life of Batista and Almond have been used. The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. At the level of descriptive statistics, statistics such as mean and standard deviation were used and at the level of inferential statistics, multivariate analysis of variance (Manawa) was used. The results showed that there is a meaningful relation between loneliness, cognitive distortions (except personalization) and attitude toward life in the second and normal wife. Cognitive distortions in the personalization component have no significant difference between the second wife and the normal wife.

Keywords: *loneliness, cognitive distortions, attitude towards life, second wife (polygamy).***Corresponding Author:**

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INTRODUCTION:

Marriage is the first and most important step in the family life cycle in which the choice of spouse takes place, and success in other stages of life depends on success in this stage [1]. Marriage is one of the general social institutions, meaning that in every society, the majority of people marry at least once in their lives. On the other hand, the habits and customs of marriage and family are not the same in all societies, but there are huge differences between communities and regions in terms of how to marry, marry with whom and with some people [2]. Since marriage is often referred to as legal, religious, and cultural methods whose nature and quality are built up with social norms, various types of family patterns can be found in different societies [3]. Colomga refers to the family of several women and single spouses in the study of various types of family structures. He has contributed Muslims to 43 percent of marriages, 43 percent to Catholic Christians, 25 percent to Catholic Christians, 25 percent to Protestant Christians and 39 percent of Laekids [4]. Anthropologists consider the origin of multidimensional emergence at the same time as a paternal sheikh, and they believe that after the domestication of animals, the issue of grazing of livestock was taken into consideration as a result of the process of land ownership. As a result, women lost their privilege and superiority, and the motivation for marriage went to sexual needs and polygamy[5]. The results of studies conducted on the families of several spouses' show that in practice one woman finds a more prominent position than the other men. This woman may be the first wife, their favorite or most noblest, or the youngest of them, who have valuable and rare resources, while in both cases there is a degree of obvious and potential conflict. Proof (Zimmel, 2005) [6] . Female married women have different attitudes to life; Gibson (2003)[7] believes that the attitude to life is an inner concept that makes reconciliation possible with stressors. Also, the attitude to life is closely related to the spiritual dimension of quality of life. Therefore, a better attitude towards life strengthens the psychological and spiritual dimensions of the individual and the quality of life of the individual. The attitude to life is described as having a sense of purpose and meaning in life [8].

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is described as having a sense of purpose and meaning in life [8]. The meaning of life (attitude towards life) is a broad concept, which is a specific structure derived from the individual cognitive system [9]. Recognizing the truth in accordance with reality is an important factor in finding the truth and aware of the positive angles of a life. Misunderstandings and misunderstandings make the human being fall into the mistake of analyzing what is happening around him, which can spark all of his life. To prevent a distortion of information in order to have a good and desirable life [10]. Beck believes that these distortions are attributed to mistakes or mistakes that serve the inferential and exploratory functions, so that they recall different ways of thinking the patient, which may even be wrong [11]. Cognitive distortions or ineffective beliefs are unreasonable in assessing them because they can lead us to the victim's life events so that they cause us troubles, sadness, discontent, and tension. Interpersonal cognitive distortions are exaggerated, very dry, irrational, and absolute beliefs about relationships or relationships in life [12]. Beck believes that the existence of cognitive errors in marital relationships causes confusion and dissatisfaction with marital life. He believes conflicting couples in their relationships have a variety of cognitive errors such as emotional reasoning, selective deployment, magnitude of bad wife behavior, diminution of husband's good behavior, speech provocation, and husband's actions [13]. The complex set of feelings and cognition, distress, and experience of negative emotions resulting from individual perceived shortcomings in private and social relationships are lonely [14]. Loneliness is a condition in which one perceives or experiences a lack of relationships with others. The feeling of loneliness includes the main elements, such as the unpleasant feeling of lack or loss of companions, the unpleasant and negative aspects of lost relationships, and the loss of the quality level of relationships with the other [15]. In other words, loneliness is a negative mental experience and distress caused by the extinction of social relationships between individuals from the context of human contact based on the need for psychological security. So loneliness does not mean a complete lack of people. But awareness of the existence of human communities and other people, in other words, in the community, is the feeling of loneliness [16]. Lack of meaning in life is one of the most common reasons among people who often or always feel lonely [17].

RESEARCH METHOD:

The present study was a descriptive, causal-comparative study. The statistical population consisted of all women of the second and normal wife of Shiraz in 2015. The sample of this study was 140 people. Sampling method was used for purposeful sample sampling for second wife

women. The sample of women who were the second wife was selected from among clients referring to counseling centers in Shiraz. A multistage cluster sampling was used to sample normal women from Shiraz. So, from the four areas of education, one district and from schools in this area, one school and two classes in school were randomly selected, and all mothers responded to the questionnaires, and after matching with age, education, the economic and social status was introduced.

Research tool

Loneliness Scale (SELSA_s): In this study, the shortened form of emotional and social loneliness

[18] was used. This scale is based on Weiss's theory (1937) [19].

Cognitive Distortion Questionnaire: This questionnaire was developed by Albert Alice and aims at assessing cognitive errors, which was standardized by Abdollah Zadeh (2010) [20].

Life Attitude Questionnaire: In this research, we used the Values (Attitude to Life) scale of Batista and Almond (1937), revised by Dobbs (1998).

Analysis method

In the present study, the data collected by SPSS software were analyzed at two levels of descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (independent t-test and multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA)).

RESULTS:

Table 1: Manova Analysis Results Loneliness in Second and Normal Wives

Squat trough	p	Test statistic	average of squares	Degrees of freedom	sum of squares	Dimensions	Source of dispersion
0.29	0.000	56.37	1189.03	1	1189.03	Romantic loneliness	group
0.33	0.000	66.85	1015.21	1	1015.21	Family loneliness	
0.14	0.000	22.00	288.58	1	288.58	Loneliness social	
			21.09	138	2910.66	Romantic loneliness	Error
			15.19	138	2095.73	Family loneliness	
			13.12	138	1809.96	Loneliness social	
				139	4099.69	Romantic loneliness	Total corrected
				139	3110.94	Family loneliness	Source of dispersion
				139	2098.54	Loneliness social	group

Table 2: Results of Manna's Analysis of Cognitive Disturbances in Second and Normal Wives

Squat trough	p	Test statistic	average of squares	Degrees of freedom	sum of squares	Cognitive distortions	Source of dispersion
0.12	0.00	19.18	52.83	1	52.83	Thinking all or not	group
0.14	0.00	23.18	80.26	1	80.26	Exaggerated generalization	
0.05	0.009	7.02	17.15	1	17.15	Mental Filter	
0.15	0.00	24.05	75.78	1	75.78	Neglecting the affair	
0.14	0.00	22.71	68.60	1	68.60	Hasty conclusion	
0.06	0.003	8.98	31.11	1	31.11	Coarse and fine-grained	
0.14	0.00	22.52	61.78	1	61.78	Emotional reasoning	
0.08	0.001	12.13	39.11	1	39.11	The phrase should be better	
0.21	0.00	36.42	113.40	1	113.40	Label	
0.02	0.088	2.95	10.31	1	10.31	Personalization	
			2.76	138	380.14	Thinking all or not	Error
			3.46	138	477.71	Exaggerated generalization	
			2/44	138	337.27	Mental Filter	

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			3.15	138	434.76	Neglecting the affair	
			3.02	138	416.80	Hasty conclusion	
			3.47	138	478.29	Coarse and fine-grained	
			2.74	138	378.64	Emotional reasoning	
			3.23	138	445.17	The phrase should be better	
			3.11	138	429.74	Label	
			3.50	138	483.26	Personalization	
				139	432.97	Thinking all or not	Total corrected
				139	557.97	Exaggerated generalization	group
				139	354.42	Mental Filter	
				139	510.54	Neglecting the affair	
				139	485.40	Hasty conclusion	
				139	509.40	Coarse and fine-grained	
				139	440.42	Emotional reasoning	
				139	484.29	The phrase should be better	
				139	543.14	Label	
				139	493.57	Personalization	

Table 3: Manova Analysis of Attitudes toward Life in Second and Normal Wives

Squat trough	p	Test statistic	average of squares	Degrees of freedom	sum of squares	Dimensions	Source of dispersion
0.21	0.000	35.81	418.31	1	418.31	The framework	group
0.34	0.000	71.14	865.03	1	865.03	Supplementary	
			11.68	138	1612.23	The framework	Error
			12.16	138	1677.94	Supplementary	
				139	2030.54	The framework	Total corrected
				139	2542.97	Supplementary	group

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

The purpose of this study was to compare the feeling of loneliness, cognitive distortions and attitude toward life in the second wife of Shiraz.

In relation to the first question of the research, is there a meaningful difference in loneliness and its components among the second and most normal women?

The results of one-variable analysis in Table 1 show that there is a significant difference between all aspects of loneliness in women of the second and normal wife, and the difference between them according to the Eta squared column for romantic loneliness, family loneliness and social loneliness is 29, 33 And 14 percent. In this regard, Homes and Dewey (2007), Liu (2007), Malver et al. (2008), Nichol et al. (2014), Dalberg and colleagues (2015), Shahini et al. (2012), Kuchaki et al. (2012), Kalantari and Hosseini Zadeh (2015), Jokar and Rustami (2015) are consistent with this research. Given the definitions of loneliness and its components, it can be said that women who marry

men for some reason (high age, divorce or widowhood, economic poverty, etc.) are some of them. They seek such a marriage to eliminate the feeling of loneliness, having a guardian or rescue from the previous situation and seek their dreams. Particularly in some societies where such marriages are less widely promoted, they are generally carried out secretly. In some cases it is public. After revealing a lot of conflicts in the family that can be found in the research findings of Mohammadi and colleagues, in polygamous marriage, as compared to monogamous families, the experience of the highest level of conflict in power relations is emotional and sexual experience. Which suggests a reduction in coherence and integrity in family relationships. In the marital relationship, the main thing is spiritual affairs, love and emotion and emotion. Similar studies in this regard can be found in Müller et al. (2001), Yoobler and Simon (2005), Homaisi and Dewey (2007), Betmaz and Cocbik (2015), Yu et al. (2016), Ebrahimi et al. (2011), Hossein Zadeh (2011). Beck believes that any bad

feeling is the result of negative thinking, and the result of this negative thinking is the individual's depression and anxiety. Research shows that the level of satisfaction in polygamous marriages is low. First, both women and men suffer from polygamy in marriage, and marital satisfaction is both low in women and men. Secondly, the rate of harm among polygamous marriages is higher than males. Thirdly In terms of distortion of roles, different results are obtained. Often, these women are upset and overweight and suffer from stress that may be traumatic or abusive. Findings of Ahmadi Research (2011). Polygamy leads to devaluation of women and psychological problems for them and their self-esteem. Women in polygamous marriage exhibited the most psychological disturbances. Physical disorders, jealousy in interpersonal relationships, depression, anxiety, phobia, paranoia These are symptoms associated with economic factors and ways of communicating with children and one's family and other family problems. So, the result can be reached in polygamous families because of conflicts in the power, emotional, and sexual relations of intimacy in this family become more diminished. In fact, first and foremost women and especially in societies where polygamy is lower, the negative attitude toward the second woman negatively affects the thoughts of the wife of the second wife, leading to a rise in cognitive distortions. According to Beck, this type of cognitive distortion is seen in the whole or in no way between couples in marital life. They have the impression that if no one is good, it's bad. If luck is not perfect, they are unhappy. Excellency is similar in the same way. For perfection, if it's not 100% perfect, it's totally bad and bad. There is no way. It's as if there was no black and white in the gray name. More than words, nobody is ever used. Along with the fact that polygamous families have enormous envy among their husbands and children, and each one likes to have all the possibilities, both emotional and financial, and to own, with the smallest it feels like nobody likes me. I'm miserable, and sometimes this is the source of conflicts and conflicts. It should be taken into account. One of the most important exaggerated cognitive distortions is extreme generalization. Sometimes our thoughts are exaggerated and difficult to change. Individuals with this type of cognitive distortion undergo a generalized exaggeration based on a particular event. For example, he "always humiliates me" or "never thinks that I have reason to" "does not respect me at all" or that "the repentance went away or life was destroyed". In many respects, the problems of humans originate from extremes. A correct and balanced understanding helps to accurately assess and plan a person so that he can achieve the best result. In this case, given the fact that there are many conflicts and conflicts in polygamous families, this family does not primarily respect

family members. And they are suppressing each other; if not by the way, this thought comes to mind that here no one respects me and despises me for my sake. The mental filter does not allow a person to see part of the reality and only to look at the limited realities that maybe that limitation is not part of reality. The individual concludes with only a small part of the information, and so the outstanding and unseen data is taken or set aside so that the individual's attitude toward the position is verified. It is almost exclusively focused on negative aspects. To be considering that in these polygamous families there are many psychiatric disorders and low self-esteem and there is a lack of sense of intimacy and trust and intercourse among polygamous women. When a person's cognitive error is high or no one is high, his mental filter goes up. In the cognitive analysis of the nasal mesh - the microbiological significance of an event, an event, or an emotion, is exaggerated or small. In this distortion or cognitive error, understanding a situation or condition is larger or smaller than what it really deserves. Whatever conflicts and plagiarism in polygamous families are greater, family members are more sensitive to all my behavior, movements and speeches, and they are exaggerated or small. In the reasoning argument, he refers to conclusions that do not support their evidence. This includes "catastrophic" reading or thinking of the worst scenario or consequences in most situations. This cognitive error in marital life also happens when one blames a person for a negative feeling and anxiety for another. This way of thinking does not come from the sense of logic. In such families, nobody takes responsibility for what he does, and he considers the mistake as someone other than himself. No correct logic confirms such a consistency. In error, some people use a lot of things for themselves and others, or give advice or instructions to others. In this kind of distortion, one expects that the situation that he wants will be a nuisance to the use of these doings and not to make life bitter, and if his own expectations are not fulfilled, he will be troubled. Hornei writes in the book "Neurotic Personality" about the concept of diodes: "People with mental illness have irrational expectations and, based on hypothetical rights, give themselves special privileges and insist that others regardless of the interests and needs Someone asks for his wishes. And since these demands are not met, the anger and frustration of his existence are exhausted, which can be deduced from the findings of Alsharbney's research (2005). Which focused on the mental and physical health of polygamous women and children, pointed out that there was a high degree of polygamy in polygamy in spite of single monogamy, resulting in lower psychological and psychological health. Polygamous women in their families have concessions that they expect their spouse to They must act, and each of them has laws

and regulations in their lives that the other party must respect and the man must judge between his spouses through justice, if he fails to comply with it becomes a conflict. In relation to the third question of the research, is there any significant difference in attitude toward life among women of the same age? The results of one-variable analysis in Table 2 indicate that there is a significant difference between the complementary and complementary components of the second and normal wife, and the difference between the Eta squared column for the framework and the complement is 21 and 34 hundredth, respectively. The researches of Snyderoffldman (2005), Dehdari et al. (2013), Aegei and Mohamadi (2013) are consistent with this variable. Here is a positive attitude to life that a positive attitude to life is a person's belief in having a framework or goal in his life that gives his life a valuable meaning. The effort to find meaning in his life is genuine and fundamental, and not secondary, from the instinctive stretch of man, this unique meaning is his own, and hence this is Him, and only He who must and is capable of realizing it, only in that case, that His sense of satisfaction will be satisfied. A person who does not have a philosophy or purpose for his life, whether his attitude towards negative life is defined according to the theory of hope as purposeful. People who have high hopes of pursuing their goals successfully and experience positive emotions more successfully. And vice versa. From the complementary component of the concept to the life of the individual's perception of living based on the framework of his choice. From the viewpoint of Bern, the person who looks positively at the peripheries and events around him, according to the findings of Mohammadi Voshiki's research (2008).

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